

SUPERSATURATION OF LIQUIDS IN LIQUIDS

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The limits of supersaturation of liquids in liquids have been studied both from theoretical and practical standpoint. It is shown that if the interfacial tension between the two participating components is sufficiently high and relative internal pressures nearly equal, definite and appreciable limits of supersaturation can be obtained.

Supersaturation of liquids in liquids still appears to be a controversial topic, and it is almost impossible to obtain a piece of convincing evidence on the either side in the literature. Rothmund (*Z. physikal.-Chem.*, 1898, 28, 443) considered the possibility of existence of such solutions although experimentally he met with negative results, a fact also supported by the experiments of Fawcett (Thesis, University of Toronto, 1912). On the other hand, the experiments of Fuchtbauer (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1904, 48, 566) gave strong evidence of existence of supersaturation although it was found to be still very low and was accounted to be "due to presence of dust particles or foreign nuclei of some sort, perhaps colloids." In order to settle these conflicting views Davis (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 1166) measured supersaturation in a few systems, and concluded that the supersaturation of liquids in liquids was a reality. But the degrees of supersaturation obtained by him are very small and do not appear to present any convincing proof of the existence of supersaturation.

The phenomenon of supersaturation in solid-liquid systems has been investigated in this laboratory for the last several years with a special technique* discussed in a previous communication (this *Journal*, 1943, 20, 183). It is proposed to apply the same technique in liquid-liquid systems to ascertain if any reliable supersaturation can be obtained.

A very important aspect of supersaturation of liquids in liquids that attracts our attention is that the interfacial tension (at least in bulk) between two liquids can be easily found out either experimentally or calculated from Antonow's rule for sparingly soluble liquids. Thus, it will be possible to examine the equation,

$$T_s - T = \frac{2M\sigma}{\rho\lambda\gamma} T_s$$

(or any other similar expression which would hold in liquids) which up to this time eluded all attempts towards a thorough examination. Besides, Kenrick's conception (University of Toronto Studies, 1913, 99, 4) that the small degree of supersaturation of liquids is connected with small interfacial tension between liquids and that there is no essential difference between supersaturated solutions of solids in liquids and those of liquids in liquids, may be tested in a more precise manner than have been done up to this time.

* This cannot be claimed to be a very accurate method but at least it avoids disturbing influences to a large extent.

We shall first try to deduce a suitable relationship for supersaturation for liquid-liquid systems. The solubility of liquids in liquids has been theoretically deduced by Hildebrand (*J. Chem. Phys.* 1933, 1, 817), Scatchard (*Chem. Rev.*, 1931, 8, 321; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 1805) and others. A simplified form of their expression for low solubility, according to Black, Joris and Taylor (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1948, 16, 541) is

$$RT \ln \frac{\alpha_1}{N_1} = V_1 \left[\left(\frac{\partial E_1}{V_1} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - \left(\frac{\partial E_2}{V_2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right]^2 \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where $\alpha_1 = f/f_0$, f being the fugacity of the solute in solution and f_0 , the fugacity of the pure solute; N_1 and V_1 denote the molar concentration and molar volume of the solute; ∂E_1 and ∂E_2 are the heats of vaporisation of solute and the solvent, and hence $\partial E_1/V_1$ and $\partial E_2/V_2$ represent approximately the respective internal pressures.

In dilute solutions (*i.e.* sparing solubility) α_1 may be taken to be unity. Therefore (1) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} -RT \ln N_1 &= V_1 \left[\left(\frac{\partial E_1}{V_1} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - \left(\frac{\partial E_2}{V_2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right]^2 \\ \text{or } \ln N_1 &= - \frac{V_1}{RT} \left[\left(\frac{\partial E_1}{V_1} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - \left(\frac{\partial E_2}{V_2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right]^2 \quad \dots \quad (2) \end{aligned}$$

Combining (2) with the equation of Thompson, *viz.*,

$$RT \ln \frac{Pr}{P_\infty} = \frac{2M\sigma}{\rho r} \quad \text{or} \quad RT \ln \frac{Sr}{S_\infty} = \frac{2M\sigma}{\rho r}$$

one gets at T

$$\begin{aligned} \ln Sr(T) &= \frac{2M\sigma}{\rho r RT} + \ln S_\infty \\ &= \frac{2M\sigma}{\rho r RT} + \ln N_1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{or } Sr(T) = A \text{ Exp. } \left[\frac{2M\sigma}{\rho r RT} - \frac{V_1}{RT} \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial E_1}{V_1} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - \left(\frac{\partial E_2}{V_2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\}^2 \right]$$

Similarly at $T + \partial T$

$$Sr(T + \partial T) = A \text{ Exp. } \left\{ \frac{2M(\sigma + \partial\sigma)}{R(T + \partial T)(\rho + \partial\rho)(r + \partial r)} - \frac{V_1}{R(T + \partial T)} \left[\left(\frac{\partial E_1}{V_1} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - \left(\frac{\partial E_2}{V_2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right]^2 \right\}$$

Equating $Sr(T)$ and $Sr(T + \partial T)$, as in solid-liquid systems, and putting for convenience

$$\left[\left(\frac{\partial E_1}{V_1} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - \left(\frac{\partial E_2}{V_2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right]^2 = I$$

one obtains

$$\frac{2M\sigma}{\rho r RT} - \frac{V_1 I}{RT} = \frac{2M(\sigma + \partial\sigma)}{R(T + \partial T)(\rho + \partial\rho)(r + \partial r)} - \frac{V_1 I}{R(T + \partial T)} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{2M\sigma}{\rho r T} - \frac{V_1 I}{T} = \frac{2M(\sigma + \partial\sigma)}{(T + \partial T)(\rho + \partial\rho)(r + \partial r)} - \frac{V_1 I}{(T + \partial T)} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

Simplifying and neglecting infinitesimals of higher order than first (4) reduces to

$$2 \left[\frac{\partial r}{r} + \frac{\partial\rho}{\rho} + \frac{\partial T}{T} - \frac{\partial\sigma}{\sigma} \right] = \frac{I r}{\sigma} \left[\frac{\partial\rho}{\rho} + \frac{\partial T}{T} \right] \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

$$\text{But } \frac{\partial\rho}{\rho} = \frac{\partial\sigma}{\sigma} \quad (\text{approx.})$$

$$\text{Therefore } 2 \left[\frac{\partial r}{r} + \frac{\partial T}{T} \right] = \frac{I r}{\sigma} \left[\frac{\partial\rho}{\rho} + \frac{\partial T}{T} \right] \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

Now $\partial\rho/\rho$ is very small as compared to $\partial T/T$, and therefore it can be neglected in comparison to $\partial T/T$. Equation (6) now becomes

$$2 \left[\frac{\partial r}{r} + \frac{\partial T}{T} \right] = \frac{I r}{\sigma} \cdot \frac{\partial T}{T}$$

$$\text{i.e. } \int \frac{\partial T}{T} = \int \frac{2\sigma}{r(I - 2\sigma)}$$

which on integration and suitable transformations yields

$$T = C \left[I - \frac{2\sigma}{r} \right] \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

Applying the condition that at $T = T_s$, $r = \infty$, one gets

$$C = \frac{T_s}{I} \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

which when combined with (7) results in

$$T_s - T = \frac{2\sigma T_s}{I r} = \frac{2\sigma T_s}{\left[\left(\frac{\partial E_1}{V_1} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - \left(\frac{\partial E_2}{V_2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right]^2} \cdot r \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

Choosing T_s to be the same in different systems Eq. (9) shows that $T_s - T$ varies directly as σ and inversely as I , if r is assumed to be constant. Hence, in order to get appreciable supersaturation σ must be as large as possible and I as small as possible, but not zero, for then r. h. s. of (9) will become infinitely great i.e. supersaturation will be infinite. This happens when liquids are miscible in all proportions for which a necessary condition is that the constituents should have similar internal pressures.

EXPERIMENTAL

The substances used were purified by standard methods and tested for purity in the usual manner (cf. Vogel, "A Text-book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 1946). Known amounts of liquids were weighed out in special test tubes (this *Journal*, 1943,

20, 183) and the required amount of the liquid solvent was added from a graduated pipette (*loc.cit.*). The tubes were sealed and heated under water in a beaker of suitable size. The beaker was heated to a temperature of about 5°-10° higher than the saturation temperature. The beaker was allowed to cool slowly (*loc.cit.*). The temperature of spontaneous separation of the solute was taken as the temperature at which the cloud appeared. This happened, in general, almost simultaneously throughout the system. The saturation temperature T_s was verified by finding out the temperature at which the cloud disappeared and reappeared. The results obtained are given in Table I.

TABLE I

System.	T_s (°C)	T (°C)	$T_s - T$
IsoAmyl alcohol in glycerol	70-71°	64.3, 64.2, 64.6, 64.4	5-6
	58-59°	52.4, 53.0, 52.5	6-7
	51-52°	46.2, 46.4, 46.4	5-6
	40°	32.6, 12.3, ..	7-8
	35°	30.0, 30.2, ...	5
Phenol in hexane	42-43°	35.0, 36.0, 35.8	7-8
	39-40°	34.0, 35.0, 34.6	7-8
Aniline in hexane	58-60°	55.2, 55.6, 55.5	3-4
	53-54°	48.8, 48.0, 49.0	4-5
	52-53°	47.2, 47.0, 47.6	5-6
	44-45°	40.0, 40.6, 41.0	4-5
	41-42°	37.0, 37.6, 37.2	4-5
Water in ethyl acetate	65-66°	42.0, 41.0, 41.6	22-23
	60-61°	38.0, 37.0, 37.6	22-23
	50-51°	32.0, 31.8, 32.4	18-19
	40-41°	Did not separate down to room temperature	...
Glycerol in acetone	80-81°	69.8, 69.4, 69.6	10-11
	69-70°	62.0, 59.8, 60.0	8-9
	60-61°	52.0, 51.8, 52.0	8-9
	55-56°	46.0, 46.0, 47.0	9-10
	50-51°	42.0, 42.6, 42.0	8-9
	45-46°	36.0, 36.0, 35.8	8-9
	40-41°	Did not separate out at 32.4°	

Almost no supersaturation has been obtained in the following system:—

Aniline in water, water in aniline, nitrobenzene in water, phenol in water, *o*-nitrophenol in water, hexane in methyl alcohol, and methyl alcohol in hexane.

With this theoretical background in view the following experimental investigations were undertaken*.

* When the solubility becomes appreciably large, the simplifications made earlier would not be justified as the value of N_1V_1 will be significant and hence the factor $N_1V_1/N_1V_1+N_2V_2$ of the original expression for solubility, cannot be put equal to unity. Under these circumstances Eq. 8) will take the form

$$T_s - T = \frac{2\sigma T_s}{r} \left[\frac{N_1V_1}{N_1V_1 + N_2V_2} \right]^2 = \frac{2\sigma T_s}{r} \left(1 + \frac{N_1V_1}{N_2V_2} \right)^2$$

which denotes that even if all other conditions are identical, supersaturation will be greater, the higher the solubility.

The results given in Table I are summarised in Table II, which gives $T_s - T$ along with σ in bulk and $T_s - T$ calculated from eq. (8) for $T_s = 300^\circ\text{K}$ for different systems. When proper values of different constant factors are substituted in (8), it simplifies to

$$T_s - T = \frac{2\sigma T_s}{I r} = \frac{\sigma}{9.88I} \quad (r = 1.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm.}) \dagger\dagger$$

TABLE II

 $T_s = 300^\circ\text{K}$

System.	σ in bulk.	I †	$T_s - T$ (observed)	$T_s - T$ (calculated)
Aniline-water	5.7	0.86	Negligible	0.7
Nitrobenzene-water	23.9	1.28	"	1.9
Phenol-water	30.0*	0.97	"	3.1
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol-water	30.0*	1.17	"	2.6
CS_2 -water	48.4**	1.52**	2**	4.0
Hexane-Me(O)H	4.4*	2.53	Negligible	0.2
Phenol-hexane	20.0*	0.89	5.6	2.3
<i>iso</i> Amyl alcohol-glycerol	24.0*	0.81	5.6	3.0
Acetone-glycerol ‡	40.0	(?)	8	...
Hexane-aniline	23.0	0.98	4.5	2.4
Water-ethyl acetate	6.0	3.54	18.0	0.2(?)

* Calculated from Antonow's rule.

** Cf. Davis (*loc.cit.*).

‡ Internal pressure not known.

† For internal pressures see Glasstone, "Recent Advances in General Chemistry", 1936, p. 265; also Mortimer (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 633).

From Table II it appears that the value of I is very nearly equal to unity in many cases. For such systems eq. (9) shows that $T_s - T$ will be approximately proportional to σ as was conceived by Kenrick (*loc.cit.*). It may be seen from the last two columns of Table II that, although there is no exact correspondence between the calculated and the observed values of $T_s - T$, there is no doubt about the fact that these are very nearly similar in most of the cases. It is clear that systems like benzene-water, toluene-water, aniline-water, nitrobenzene-water and *vice versa*, hexane-methyl alcohol, methyl alcohol-hexane etc., will have negligible supersaturation ($< 1^\circ$) as is corroborated by experimental evidence recorded in Table II. The apparent anomaly of ethyl acetate-water system can be accounted to be due to compound formation (Glasstone, "Recent

†† After Davis (*loc.cit.*). Frenkel ("Kinetic Theory of Liquids", 1946, p. 374) suggests $r \approx 2 \times 10^{-6}$ cm. for nucleus droplet of water in stable equilibrium with water vapour at 373°K .

Advances in General Chemistry", 1936, p. 258) and hence a large $T_s - T$ results. In the case of phenol-water system, it is very probable that σ is not correctly given by Antonow's rule which holds only when the solubility is very low.

Table I shows clearly that supersaturation in liquid-liquid systems does exist, only we have to choose suitable systems for a clear manifestation *i.e.* systems with large σ and small I , as for example, systems like acetone-glycerol, phenol-hexane, isoamyl alcohol-glycerol, etc. Exact correspondence between calculated and observed $T_s - T$ should not be expected, however, due to uncertainties in the value of ' r ' even if σ and I are taken to be correctly known.

There is another remarkable fact which must be pointed out at this place. The cloud of separating solute (specially in cases of low solubility) appears almost simultaneously throughout the system. In other words, nucleus formation appears to occur throughout the systems almost at the same time, quite contrary to the mode of separation of the solid solute from a supersaturated solution. Besides, no stabilising effect of continued and prolonged heating has been observed in these systems. From what has been said above it is obvious that no heating effect is possible under these conditions of easy nucleus formation. It appears that as in liquid-liquid separation, no work is to be done for properly orientating the nucleus forming units into a lattice whose formation would involve a considerably larger amount of work than in the formation of a mere droplet of radius ' r '. Hence, it is extremely easy for the solute molecules to form a nucleus as they move and meet their respective species. The difference in the internal pressures always tends to throw one out of the other, and hence the same molecular species will have a very strong tendency to go together in presence of another molecular species having a widely different internal pressure. Obviously, then, the supersaturation will be negligible in such cases as the difference in their internal pressures helps to reduce the necessary amount of work to be performed for nucleus formation. These reasons probably account for easy separating out of sparingly soluble liquids from their supersaturated solutions.